

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATOR'S COMPETENCE AND STUDENT'S ENTREPRENEURIAL INTEREST

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Abstract

Entrepreneurship educator's competence stands as a strong determining factor in implementing entrepreneurship education initiatives that would make meaningful effects both on the student's interest and consequently on the economy through the student's exhibition of entrepreneurial behaviours. This study discussed entrepreneurship educator's competence effect on student's entrepreneurial interest. The study's objective was to consider the influence of an entrepreneurship educator's competence on a student's entrepreneurial interest. A sample size of 370 students was surveyed and the responses were analysed using the SmartPLS tool. The result showed a strong influence of the educator's competences on student's entrepreneurial interest. One amongst other competences was the educator's knowledge and application in an actual enterprise. The study recommended that for entrepreneurship educators to be able to deliver sustainable quality education the criteria for choosing educators should go beyond a basic business education background to actual entrepreneurial qualities and better certifications.

Keywords; entrepreneurship education, entrepreneurial interest, educator's competence.

I. INTRODUCTION

Entrepreneurship educators are considered the forerunners of ensuring quality entrepreneurship education that can promote entrepreneurial activities amongst students. The entrepreneurship educator's competence is of great importance to a student's learning process because qualities that are applicable to business practise and experience are needed to develop students' entrepreneurial skills (Ibidunni, Peter, Amahian, & Ogbari, 2017). Educators need to first have a clear understanding of the meaning of the concept of entrepreneurship in an effort to operationalize the development and evaluation of competence in their academic settings. This is especially important when developing an appropriate education and training programme for future entrepreneurs. As a result, an educator's ability to appropriately impart knowledge to the student requires that the educator must have gone through required training and have some experience that can be passed on to the students. Bădulescu, Bădulescu, Csintalan, & Simuț, (2019).

The study by Bauman and Lucy (2021) identifies the path to entrepreneurship starting with an interest to become an entrepreneur; this is in line with the study by Yamakawa, McKone-Sweet, Hunt, & Greenberg (2016), who identified that in building student's interest, it is imperative for students to acquire practical knowledge through direct engagement in entrepreneurial endeavours. While many other studies focus competency development on students (Wang, Yueh, & Wen, 2019; Chaker, & Jarraya, 2021); other studies focused on pedagogic competence (Bell & Bell 2020). In this order, study has also shown that despite the prevalence of programs designed to encourage and support entrepreneurs, few graduates actively pursue or even consider entrepreneurship as a career option. One of the most challenging aspects for educators is the action-oriented nature of the subject matter, which is concerned with how to put learned information into action while also assisting students in developing the ability to put knowledge into action (Neck & Corbett, 2018). Studies on educator's competencies have largely focused on their educational training or having a background in entrepreneurship (Zappe, Hochstedt, Kisenwether, & Shartrand, 2013; Wraae, & Walmsley, 2020); for example many educators have certificates in business management or have taken entrepreneurship courses. Emphasis are being laid majorly on educational qualifications and then back-up is sought from those in the field to come in for public lectures and other events during the student's academic journey. More studies have shown that many educators in the field of entrepreneurship have only had cursory training in education and pedagogy, forcing them to fend for themselves as they develop their own pedagogical practices (Neck & Corbett, 2018; Bell & Bell 2020). This study seeks to conceptualise better the kind of competencies an educator should possess to be more effective in building student's entrepreneurial interest sustainably. The objective of this study is to probe further into competencies that educator's require to administer entrepreneurship education that have a positive effect on student's entrepreneurial interest.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Entrepreneurship education

Entrepreneurship education has become a globally adopted tool for ensuring we build a more stable economic environment as it nurtures student's entrepreneurial capacity and mindset, as well as to encourage successful entrepreneurship among students (Huang, An, Liu, Zhuo, & Wang, 2020). According to Wu, and Wu, (2017), entrepreneurship education improves students' enthusiasm to establish a firm and also has an effect on their growth performance. The various experiences that make up entrepreneurship education give students the skills and perspective needed to seize and transform opportunities. It extends beyond

starting a business. It aims to improve students' capacity to foresee and react to society changes. The entirety of EE is centred on training students to be bold and creative enough to start their own venture and be resilient in the face of all odds, seeking their own place as they build sustainable income.

Bell and Bell (2020) in their study introduced the educational theories in explaining entrepreneurship education they developed a model that reflects the educator's role and the learner's place in appropriating entrepreneurship education. They also reviewed seminal education theories and philosophies of constructivism, theory of experiential learning and theory of transformative learning. They argued that an objectivist approach to learning serves a complimentary role to the constructivist learning approach and are both important to the learning process of students. Furthermore, they focused on the tasks of the educator and the student in experiential entrepreneurial education across further and higher education, based on educational theories and concepts that guide the learning process. Similarly, Hagg and Gabriellson (2019), emphasised on educator's adoption of a more constructivist approach to teaching. Macht and Ball (2016), also asserted that entrepreneurship educators should make links to real-life experiences that appear to be valuable to learners. The idea is to make the process of entrepreneurship education more active than passive by engaging the minds of students through activities that aid learning by doing. Similarly, Kaynardag, (2019) in her study asserted that instructors' pedagogical abilities play a critical role in increasing the overall quality of teaching and learning in higher education institutions. The study investigated how instructors' pedagogical competencies affect students' opinions of their instructors by concentrating on three essential elements of classroom pedagogy: delivery, communication, and assessment. Meanwhile in the study carried out by Foliard, Pontois, Fayolle, and Diermann, (2018); they asserted that The more actual professional experience in business that an educator has, the more competent he or she will be in taking students in an Entrepreneurship Education programme; the more professional experience a teacher has, the more predisposed he or she will be to lead EE; also, business-related training for teachers has a positive impact on the EE practises of teachers in a positive manner. Furthermore, Olokundun, Ibidunni, Peter, Amaihian, and Ogbari (2017) their findings also emphasised the importance of the educators competence with the claim that in order for the educator to instil entrepreneurial knowledge in students, it is necessary for them to have actual business skills and experience.

Educator's Competence

The educator's role in every learning process is one which is crucial, it therefore cannot be overlooked. The educator's role has been described as both conceptually and pedagogically demanding (Wraae, & Walmsley, 2020). The focus on entrepreneurship educator's competence reflects much on the educator's ability to engage creative teaching methods based on their development or training, considering the educator's background as it relates to entrepreneurship. In the study by Ogbari, Olokundun, Ibidunni, Obi, and Akpoanu, (2019) Competence was assessed based on the perspective of the outcomes attained or the inputs utilised. The teacher's competency can be observed by several indicators, such as test scores, the overall satisfaction of students, and the level of student engagement in the classroom. Owenvbiugie, and Ojeaga, (2022) in their study included networking competency asides pedagogical and problem solving competencies. The pedagogical competencies have been identified by several studies to be relevant to student's effective learning and interest (Abdul, 2017; Owenvbiugie, & Ojeaga, 2022). The perceptions that educators have of their future roles as well as their perceptions of entrepreneurship are investigated in some of the studies that look at the training of entrepreneurship educators. Furthermore, other research regard the entrepreneurship educator's competence as a valuable subject since it fosters among other things initiative, personal responsibility for learning, the development of enthusiasm, and an awareness of the value of freedom (Lepistö & Rönkkö, 2013; Deveci, & Seikkula-Leino, 2018).

Entrepreneurial Interest of Students

Building students' entrepreneurial interest has become tougher as a result of the entrepreneurship climate in many nations today. Reports by the General entrepreneurship monitor for the year 2020-2021 show instability persist in a variety of business areas; though this can be taken as an opportunity for more opportunities, it would require more resilience on the entrepreneur's part. Studies show that more than half of the entrepreneurs believe that it is harder to start a business and thus affecting individual interest (GEM, 2022).

Entrepreneurial interest must be encouraged in order to grow, it must first be nurtured. Educational institutions should aid students in growing as well as in strengthening the entrepreneurial spirit of students and faculty members (Surjanti, Nugrohoseno, & Musfidah, 2018). Because of the high participation rate of educated people in the labour sector, a remedy for the problem of youth unemployment is an increase in the number of young people who are interested in starting their own businesses. When looking at entrepreneurial desire, most research have concentrated on the factors that influence the decision to become an entrepreneur, while giving little attention to the actual process of starting a business (Osakede, Lawanson, & Sobowale, 2017).

Studies have shown certain aspect that affect entrepreneurial interest of students. According to (Osakede, Lawanson, & Sobowale, 2017), the factors affecting the entrepreneurial interest of students could be push or pull factors. The push factors such unemployment, poverty and the need for job security; these are basically negative factors that influence the interest of individuals to become entrepreneurial. The pull factors on the other hand are considered positive factors that influence the desire to be entrepreneurial such as; the opportunity to make use of one's own creative abilities, independence, solving identified problems to make life better for members of one's society and the prospect of earning more money. The focus of this study is to focus on factors that encourage the pull factors in a student's entrepreneurial interest; this requires quality entrepreneurship education.

Quality education that is able to have a positive effect on the students is most required in the educational sector today. Education should have a clear view of purpose: just as purported by Biesta (2009) Purposeful education is an evidence-based profession, with the belief that "the kind of progressive, systematic development" in education can only be achieved through large-scale experimental investigations and thorough evaluation of the correlation between input and output. The idea is focusing on how teaching and learning actually occur in order to isolate the factors that truly matter for improving educational outcomes, which is one of the roles UNESCO is playing for member nations who seem to be lagging behind in accessing quality education (UNESCO, 2022). An educator's role is crucial in the learning process of entrepreneurship education, the input the educator makes highly influences the output of the student's interest. Thus, being particular about the competence of an educator is necessary for effectiveness in fulfilling a sustainable agenda for entrepreneurship education.

Theoretical Review: Theory of Planned Behaviour

The theory of planned behaviour by Ajzen (1985) explains behavioural interest by three variable which include; the perceived behavioural control which asserts that control factors lead to either perceived ease or difficulty in the performance of the behaviour. Some of the factors include the availability or lack of time, money, and other resources; the collaboration of others; the requisite skills and competencies which the student feels they have some level of control over (Ajzen, 2020). The subjective norm and attitude towards the behaviour also influences the student's interest in being entrepreneurial; these factors

mentioned can be influenced by the educator since the learning process of the students is largely handled by the educators (Wraae, & Walmsley, 2020).

The attitude towards a behaviour pertains to the extent to which an individual holds a positive or negative assessment or judgement of said behaviour, such as the initiation of actions towards establishing a new business venture. The higher an individual's impression of positive outcomes resulting from entrepreneurial endeavours, the more favourable their attitude towards engaging in such behaviour should be. As a result, their intention to participate in these activities becomes stronger. Subjective norm pertains to the individual's perception of the societal pressure exerted upon them to engage in or abstain from a particular action. This pertains to the views around the endorsement or disapproval of significant individuals or groups regarding an individual's decision to initiate the process of establishing a new business, and the degree to which this endorsement or disapproval holds significance for the individual. Furthermore, perceived behavioural control pertains to an individual's subjective assessment of the level of ease or difficulty associated with executing a specific behaviour. The behaviour in question is influenced by control beliefs pertaining to the availability or lack of necessary resources and opportunities. There is a positive correlation between the level of perceived behavioural control and the strength of an individual's interest in engaging in an entrepreneurial venture (Ajzen, 1991; Tornikoski, & Maalaoui, 2019). These variables are traceable to the competencies to student's interest as they each reflect how entrepreneurship educators can better influence student's interest through their visible mirroring of the roles of entrepreneurs as well as instilling learned skills from actual experiences.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative approach in examining the entrepreneurship educator's competence effect on student's entrepreneurial interest. Using a cross-sectional survey method data was obtained from the respondents. The population for the study included undergraduate students of a prestigious higher institution which was chosen because of its track record of alumni and current students who have successful start-ups. They also teach entrepreneurship to all students from the first semester to the final semester of their academic journey. The sample size was derived to be 370 from a total population of over 7 thousand students and a total of 357 valid questionnaires were recorded making 96.4% response rate.

The study employed a multiple sampling technique which included purposive, stratified, and simple random sampling. Purposive sampling was used in selecting the institution focused on in this study, the students were divided into strata and then simple random sampling to distribute the instrument (questionnaire). Smart PLS was used to measure for common method bias, reliability, validity and the Path relationship between entrepreneurship education and the entrepreneurial intention of students.

Results and Discussion

Questionnaires were administered to the respondents and analyses were done using SMARTPLS. The null hypothesis was presented as:

H₀: Educator's competence has no significant impact on a student's entrepreneurial interest

Hypothesis one was analysed using Structural equation modelling on SMARTPLS. This model utilises various instruments in the analysis. Convergent validity assessment is required to ensure that the measurement validity of each variable is achieved. The convergent validity assessment includes loadings, Cronbach's Alpha (CA), average variance extracted (AVE), and composite reliability (CR). Loading is expected to be higher than 0.5 provided the AVE value larger than 0.5 is achieved. Cronbach Alpha is

expected to be above 0.6, value between 0.7 - 0.9 are considered satisfactory. AVE is expected to be higher than 0.50, and CR is expected to be 0.7 - 0.9.

Table 1: Factor loading for Educator's Competence and Student's Entrepreneurial Interest

	Factor loading	VIF	Cronbach alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Indicator's	> 0.7	< 0.5	≥0.7		≥0.8	≥0.5
Educator's Competence						
Appofkno Assessarcc Instrmast Varofmat	0.798	1.340	0.706	0.732	0.815	0.526
	0.707	1.294				
	0.749	1.369				
	0.636	1.312				
Student's Entrepreneurial Interest						
Involvact Mindset Newidea	0.798	1.389	0.649	0.709	0.805	0.583
	0.622	1.186				
	0.851	1.320				

Cronbach's Alpha (CA) for all constructs is satisfied (Table 1), they are between 0.6 and 0.9. Item deletion was conducted for items that have loading less than 0.6. After deleting the lowest loading item, the AVE increased from 0.526 to 0.608. Therefore, all AVE values are satisfied (larger than 0.5) (Table 1). The AVE and CR values of the constructs of variables were obtained and gave AVE and CR are 0.805 and 0.861 respectively, then all CR values are satisfied. Reliability and validity measures for the constructs are shown in Table above.

Table 2: Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Fornell-Larcker Criterion		
	Educator's Competence	Student's Entrepreneurial Interest
Educator's Competence	0.725	
Student's Entrepreneurial Interest	0.352	0.763

Table 3: Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)

Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT)			
	Educator's Competence	Student's Interest	Entrepreneurial Interest
Educator's Competence			
Student's Interest	Entrepreneurial Interest	0.475	

Discriminant validity is the extent to which a construct is truly distinct from other constructs by empirical standards (Avkiran & Ringle, 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2020). Discriminant validity assessments include Fornell-Larcker criteria, cross-loadings, and Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio. The assessment is to ensure that each variable in the model is different from one to another. Cross loadings should be lower than loading within the construct. Cross loadings are satisfying, loadings of each indicator are the highest for their designated constructs. Fornell-Larcker's criterion needs the square root of AVE of a construct to be larger than the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model. The Fornell-Larcker criteria are satisfied (Table 2). The HTMT stringent criterion requires the HTMT value to be less than 0.85 (Kline, 2011). HTMT criteria are satisfied, all HTMT values are below 0.85 (Table 3). It is confirmed that discriminant validity is achieved.

Structural model assessment

After we confirm that all the indicators of the variables are reliable and valid from the tables above, the next step is to assess the structural model. Since the PLS-SEM algorithms use the iteration method for multiple regression series, the path coefficient in PLS-SEM represents the regression coefficients including coefficient of determination (R^2), variance inflation factor (VIF), effect size to R^2 (f^2). The VIF values indicate collinearity between exogenous and endogenous constructs relationship (Avkiran & Ringle, 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2020). The same measure in multiple regression is applied, the recommended VIF values < 3.3 or < 5 are acceptable for all variable predictors in the model (Avkiran & Ringle, 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2020). All VIF values are above (Table 3), indicating that there is no collinearity problem interfering with our results. The coefficient of determination (R^2) indicates the model's predictive accuracy and also represents the amount of variance in the endogenous construct explained by all of the exogenous constructs linked to it (Ringle et al., 2020).

Table 4: R square

R Square	
Student's Entrepreneurial Interest	0.124

Table 5: F square

	Educator's Competence	Student's Interest	Entrepreneurial
Educator's Competence		0.142	
Student's Interest			Entrepreneurial

The R^2 value of 0.75, 0.50, or 0.25 is suggested to be substantial, moderate, or weak respectively (Avkiran & Ringle, 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2020). Previous suggestion, the R^2 value of 0.02, 0.13, and 0.26 were considered small, medium, and substantial respectively (Cohen, 2013; Muller, 1989). In between, the R^2 value of 0.19, 0.33, and 0.67 indicating weak, moderate, and substantial respectively was suggested (Chin, 1998). In this research, Student's Entrepreneurial Interest can be explained by the predictor variable of Educator's Competence with the value of R^2 of 0.124 (Table 4). It indicates that the relationship strength is sufficient. The coefficient of determination above 0.20 can be considered high in some disciplines, but values between 0.25 and 0.50 are considered good. The effect size to R^2 (f^2) indicates the degree of the impact of an independent construct on a dependent construct (Avkiran & Ringle, 2018; Sarstedt et al., 2020). The f^2 value of 0.35, 0.15, or 0.02 is suggested to be substantial, medium, or weak respectively (Cohen, 2013; Muller, 1989). The effect size value of each predictor variable in the model ranges from 0.142 to 0.330 (Table 5) which are included in the category of small to medium.

Hypothesis Path Analysis of Educator's Competence and Student's Entrepreneurial Interest

Table 6 and Figure 1.1 below both show the relationship between educator's competence and student's entrepreneurial interest. The coefficient parameter and the significant value generated from the 95% bias corrected confidence intervals of each independent variable are reflected. The path coefficient provides a significant value (at the $p = 0.05$ level). Hypotheses testing was done by using the one-tailed test since it is appropriate to test one direction relationship.

Table 6: Path value for Educator's Competence -> Student's Entrepreneurial Interest

	Path value	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P Values
Educator's Competence - > Student's Entrepreneurial Interest	0.352	0.368	0.055	6.357	0.000

Figure 1.1: Path Analysis of Educator's Competence and Student's Entrepreneurial Interest

The value of the coefficient (β) to the relationship of Educator's Competence \rightarrow Student's Entrepreneurial Interest is 0.352 with a p-value < 0.05 . This means that the null Hypothesis (H_0) is not supported; the alternative H_1 is supported. This shows that educator's competence accounts for 35.2% of student's entrepreneurial interest; this invariably means an improvement in educator's competence will improve the interest of students

Discussion of Results

Based on the findings from the study conducted by the researcher, the empirical results are discussed below:

Hypothesis one stated that "educator's competence has no significant effect on student's entrepreneurial interest". The test results show that a significant relationship exists between educator's competence and student's entrepreneurial interest at a significance level of 0.000. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected; this implies that certain criteria need to be put in place to ensure educators are better fit to impact knowledge in students such that their interest is triggered as well as sustained. The statistics in this study show that most students agree that the educator's competence in teaching has impacted on their entrepreneurial interest. These findings are in line with the study conducted by Citrawandi, and Susanto, (2020) who asserted that the lecturer's competence has a significant effect on student entrepreneurial intention. This is also in line with Iwu, Opute, Nchu, Eresia-Eke, Tengeh, Jaiyeoba, and Aliyu, (2021) affirmed in their study that The students' perceptions of the lecturing team's level of competency show a moderately positive link with their intentions to pursue entrepreneurship.

Conclusion

The findings of this research show that the educator's competence invariably affects student's entrepreneurial interest. There is then a need to ensure the educators receive the appropriate training required to ensure they are able remain relevant to the teaching of entrepreneurship. Although there is a need to emphasise on qualifications that make an educator fit so proper assessments can be made

Recommendations

Ensuring the competence level of educator's handling the course is paramount to the successful transfer of knowledge. Therefore, it is necessary for educators to have more than just a basic business certificate, more entrepreneurial qualities should inform the criteria for deciding who would teach entrepreneurship contents to the student. Also, the place experts coming in to give more insight on what is obtainable in the industry should still be emphasised. This will ensure a wholesome learning experience of the students which will aid their decision faster on venturing into entrepreneurship.

AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Our paper, Entrepreneurship Educator's Competence and Student's Entrepreneurial Interest, is unique and has never been published. Every piece of information is true, responsibly gathered, and properly cited from outside sources. The text guarantees participant confidentiality by adhering to ethical requirements. We promise not to post it anywhere without editorial permission if it is

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